

Mozi 墨子

By Maddalena Poli, University of Pennsylvania

Entry tags: Text, Early Chinese text, Philosophical writings, Religious Group, Early Chinese Traditions

Ancient Chinese philosophical text that would become foundational to the philosophical current known as Mohism. Attributed to a thinker known as Mozi, the text's importance lies in constituting the first extant challenge to ideas later labeled as Confucian. ___ The Mozi 墨子, also known as Mojing 墨經, is a text traditionally attributed to thinker Mo Di 墨翟. Very little is known about Mo Di. The biography recorded in the Records of the Historian 史記 one of the briefest, and presents Mo Di as a man from the state of Song 宋 (conquered by the Qin 秦 state in 286), who was skilled at defensive works and practicing frugality. He is said to have lived during or after Confucius's times, in the 5th century BCE. The Yi wen zhi 藝文志, the oldest extant catalogue collected in the Hanshu 漢書 describes the Mozi as a book of 71 chapters 篇. The current edition is however of 53 chapters; Johnston (The Mozi, page xxvii) suggests that 18 chapters were thus lost between the Han and the Song dynasties (i.e., between the second and thirteenth century CE), but Bi Yuan 畢沅 (1730-1797 CE) annotated in the Lushi chungiu 呂氏春秋 that "the book of Mozi originally had 71 chapters, today 16 have been lost" (Lushi chungiu jishi 呂氏春秋集釋 15.363, 2009 Zhonghua shoji edition), suggesting that perhaps two more chapters were lost after the 18th century. Of these 18 chapters, there is only a record of 8 titles. No content has survived. ___ Little has emerged from ancient manuscripts that may help recovering missing steps in the formation of this text. Decades after the recovery of Xinyang 信陽 bamboo manuscripts (1957), Li Xueqin 李學勤 identified a handful of them as the Mozi. This content is not part of the received Mozi that we see today; it was recorded in an edition circulating until the Tang dynasty, but was later lost. According to preliminary introductions, the Anda University collection of manuscripts also include some passages related to the text of the Mozi (Huang Dekuan 2017). This confirms previous suggestions that at least part of the Mozi was composed during the Warring States era (453-221BCE), with then additional textual material that became part of what today is the Mozi. None of the authors of this text's sections can be identified. ___ As noted in the scholarship (Johnston; Goldin), a peculiar feature of the textual history of the Mozi is its "disappearance" from the Qin dynasty (221 BCE - 206 BCE) onwards, until the text become widely available as part of the Daoist Canon 道藏, published in 1447. The records of commentaries are scarce, and the commentaries themselves have not been preserved (Johnston xxvii). Following this publication, it took another few centuries for Chinese scholars to rediscover this work. The major studies of the Mozi date to the Qing dynasty (1644-1911 CE). The current shape of the text is due to the work of the above mentioned Bi Yuan. Because of the secluded life of the text, it is very likely that the remaining 53 chapters correspond quite closely to what was catalogued during the Han dynasties. ___ The current structure of the Mozi is divided as follows: A) the Core Chapters, 1 to 7; B) the eleven "core" doctrines, from 8 to 39. each doctrine at some point included three sections (labeled as 上中下). Of these 33 chapters, 25 only survive. C) the canons, 經 (two chapters); D) the explanations 經說, 2 chapters; E) three chapters, two referred as "the choosing" chapters, 取, and one named Geng Zhu 耕柱; F) four chapters in the form of dialogues, 47 to 50; G) the remaining chapters, eleven in total. ___ In terms of its content, the Mozi represents a set of ideas that are often considered to be a response to values later identified as Confucian. A central theme in the Mozi is that of "impartial caring" 兼愛, that is to say, the idea that individuals should care for each other impartially, regardless of one's relationship to one another. Human are those who promote what is good for the world, not for oneself or one's family (仁人之事者, 必務求興天下之利, 兼愛下). The figure of Mozi was attributed frugality perhaps in light of the text's arguments against lavish uses of music (非樂 in 3 chapters, of which one has been preserved), and in favor to moderating funeral rituals (節葬, originally 3 chapters of which one has been preserved) and expenditure (節用, two of three chapters have been preserved). The arguments are developed from the same logic: if something does not benefit all society alike, then the way in which it is conducted must be changed. For example, extravagant funerals should be encouraged if they enriched the poor, gave abundance,

corrected perils and governed chaos (厚葬久喪實可以富貧眾寡，定危治亂乎，此仁也，義也). Because this is not the case, those in charge should discourage it. ___ Heaven is also a critical topic, which is addressed primarily in three chapters titled “Heaven’s Will” 天志. Heaven is also referenced in other sections of this work, but one ought not haste to find a unified conception of Heaven or other subjects, given that the “Mozi” almost certainly is the result of multiple hands. As it happens with many other ancient texts, it is more appropriate to talk of common themes shared across multiple chapters. On the basis of these three chapters, Heaven can be summarized as an entity that desires what is right over what is wrong (“Heaven desires righteousness and abominates unrighteousness, 天欲義而惡不義” Legge’s translation); it sets standard for ruling and proper government, and cares for all people, 天之愛天下之百姓. Because Heaven is unavoidable, one ought to take what it desires and wants as model, and act accordingly: “The will of Heaven to me is like the compasses to the wheelwright and the square to the carpenter, 我有天志，譬若輪人之有規，匠人之有矩.” Because of this, Kirkland has defined the Mozi’s view of Heaven completely subservient to the socio-political philosophy of this text.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 200 CE

Region: Warring States China

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

Generated with guidance from Professor Armin Selbitschka. a) The eastern part of Gansu (especially the Fangmatan site near Tianshui; excavation report: Wenwu 1989.2: 1-11 and 31; for the sake of convenience, I will attach a digital copy of the report below) b) Shaanxi c) Shanxi d) Hebei e) Henan f) Shandong g) Jiangsu h) Anhui i) Zhejiang j) Hubei k) Hunan

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 墨子閒詁 Mozi xian gu, edited by Sun Yirang 孫詒讓 (1848 – 1908), various editions
- Source 2: 墨子校注 Mozi jiao zhu, edited by Wu Yujiang 吳毓江 (1898 – 1977). Additional annotation to Sun’s edition. 2006, Zhonghua Shuju
- Source 3: Yan Lingfeng 嚴靈峰. Wuqiubeizhai Mozi Jicheng 無求備齋墨子集成, 46 vols. Taipei: Chengwen chubanshe, 1975.

Notes: Wuqiubeizhai Mozi Jicheng 無求備齋墨子集成: a collection of all the editions of the text Mozi. Some are available only as part of this set.

Reference: Yao-Cheng Chang. An Exceptional Portrait of Yang Zhu and Mozi Beyond the Mencian Track. *Asian Studies*, 9(1) doi: <https://doi.org/10.4312/as.2021.9.1.203-224>.

Reference: MEYER Andrew Seth. ‘Only the Human Way May Be Followed’: Reading the Guodian Manuscripts against the Mozi.

Reference: Michael NYLAN. Kongzi and Mozi, the Classicists (Ru 儒) and the Mohists (Mo 墨) in Classical-Era Thinking..

Reference: Xueqin Li. 《長台關竹簡中的〈墨子〉佚篇》. (Xueqin Li), 《徐中舒先生九十壽辰紀念文集》.. 四川·巴蜀書社.

Reference: Sun Zhuocai 孫卓彩. 墨學概要. 齊魯書社出版社.

Reference: Angus Graham. Later Mohist Logic, Ethics, and Science. The Chinese University of Hong Kong Press.

Reference: Zheng Jiewen 郑杰文. Zhongguo Mo xue tongshi 中国墨学通史. 2 vols. Beijing: renmin chubanshe.

Reference: Watanabe Takashi 渡邊卓. “Bokushi shohen no chosaku nendai” 「墨子」諸篇の著作年代. Tōyō Gakuhō 東洋學報, 45(3)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/mohism/>
- Source 1 Description: Description of Mohism and Mozi by Chris Fraser
- Source 1 URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mohism>
- Source 1 Description: Wikipedia Entry on Moshim. Fairly accurate; good reading list
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Mohism>
- Source 2 Description: Britannica Entry on Mohism
- Source 3 URL: <https://baike.baidu.com/item/墨子/245>
- Source 3 Description: Baidu entry on Mozi and Mohism. Good account of what the sources tell us, but does not question their historical validity.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://faculty.franklin.uga.edu/kirkland/sites/faculty.franklin.uga.edu.kirkland/files/MOTZU.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: study of some of Mozi's aspects by Russell Kirkland
- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/mozi>
- Source 1 Description: Text version. Not citable, but freely accessible
- Source 2 URL: <http://publish.ancientbooks.cn/docShuju/platform.aspx>
- Source 2 Description: 墨子閒話 Mozi xian gu, Zhonghua publisher edition. It requires subscription.
- Source 3 URL: <http://publish.ancientbooks.cn/docShuju/platform.aspx>
- Source 3 Description: 墨子校注 Mozi jiao zhu, Zhonghua publisher edition. It requires subscription.

Reference: Hui-chieh Loy Mozi (Mo-tzu, c. 400s–300s B.C.E.)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Notes: Decades after the recovery of Xinyang bamboo manuscripts (1957), Li Xueqin 李學勤 identified a handful of them as the Mozi. This content is not part of the received Mozi that we see today; it was recorded in an edition circulating until the Tang dynasty, but was later lost. According to preliminary introductions, the Anda University collection of manuscripts also include some passages related to the text of the Mozi (Huang Dekuan 2017). In later ages, it was written on paper.

Reference: Li Xueqin. 《長台關竹簡中的〈墨子〉佚篇》. 《徐中舒先生九十壽辰紀念文集》. 四川·巴蜀書社.

Reference: Huang Dekuan 黃德寬. Anhui Daxue Cang Zhanguo Zhujian Gaishu 安徽大學藏戰國竹簡概述.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown. Field knows too little about these processes, of which only the written media survive.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely no.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Chris Fraser identifies religious elements, and thus sees Mozi as foundational to a religious movement. Yet, there is no entity close to the figure of god in the Judeo-Christian tradition. Heaven rewards and punishes individuals; but other aspects associated with a Judeo-Christian god are not present, such as creating the world; caring for people; accepting their repentance. See <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/mohism/>

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Potentially, anyone who could read or be taught this text. Women were almost certainly excluded.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are records of different versions, e.g. one abridged, but they are almost all lost. These versions were lost; from records scattered in other sources, the differences among these seem to have been minor. See discussion in Johnston, *The Mozi*, Introduction; and Goldin 2011.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: We know of the existence of various editions of this text, they possibly differed both in the text itself and its interpretations. We have however no other edition than the one that was preserved in the Daoist canon. Thus determining what these differences may have been is currently mainly based on conjecture. The forthcoming publications of the Anhui University collection may cast light on this. See also introduction in Johnston, "The Mozi".

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Content of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It had been transmitted as part of the Daoist Canon 道藏 (see Goldin 2011). What exactly is the canonization assigned to the Mozi in this collection, remains unclear.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: It will later be preserved as part of the Daoist Canon (see Goldin 2011).

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The Canon 經 sections appear to be list of vocabulary. For each word a definition is provided, followed by further explanations (perhaps the latter are a second layer of commentarial tradition).

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is very difficult to recover the textual history of the Mozi

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The Mozi details several social norms and discusses legal aspects; but it does not express a *formal* legal code. For example, in the essays Fei Gong 非攻 the text condemns offensive war. There is no evidence that this becomes other than a position expressed in this work.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: If one considers the text's belief in the existence of spirits and ghosts a form of body/mind dualism. Spirits and ghosts are primarily discussed in the Ming gui 明鬼 chapter, where the arguments seem to be promoting the socio-political views of the author(s) more than else (see below). In other sections, spirits are mentioned but their existence is not questioned. In "Heaven's will", spirits act as intermediaries for Heaven; in "Shang tong" 尚同, praying to spirits will prevent punishments from Heaven, as if pleasing the spirits also meant, somehow, pleasing Heaven.

Reference: Roel Sterckx undefined. MOZI 31: EXPLAINING GHOSTS, AGAIN. (Carine Defoort, Nicolas Standaert), *The Mozi as an Evolving Text*. Brill.

Reference: Erica Brindley. "The Perspicuity of Ghosts and Spirits" and the Problem of Intellectual Affiliations in Early China. *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 129(2)

Reference: Benjamin Wong. War and Ghosts in Mozi's Political Philosophy. *Philosophy East and West*, 54(3)

Reference: Piotr Gibas. MOZI AND THE GHOSTS: THE CONCEPT OF MING 明 IN MOZI'S "MING GUI" 《明鬼》. doi: doi:10.1017/eac.2016.23.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: as the chapter "Ming qui" 明鬼 details, ghosts can deliver punishments or rewards to the living, depending on how they are being treated. They are so powerful that humans cannot contrast them.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: Yet note that ghosts and spirits have bodies too. But they may have animal bodies, or none at all.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Notes: If by "distinct notions of psychological states" it is meant discussions of desires, emotions, reflections on how to make decisions, fears, etc.

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

Notes: The text in fact does not elaborate a theory on emotions (qing 情) or desires (yu 欲); but because the expectation is that of behaving in ways that favor the group rather than the self, I labeled them as "generally positive." ___ Virag (2017) interprets in some

passages qing 情 as affective emotions, but it more likely refers to "circumstances, truths." See also references attached. As for desires, both Heaven and humans are assigned the ability to desire, but that is a statement of fact, such as "all men desired rewards" (in the 尚同下 chapter), or "Heaven desires people to care for each other and profit each other, 天欲人相愛相利" (in 法儀 chapter).

Reference: Virág Curie. *The Emotions in Early Chinese Philosophy*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Reference: Bongrae Seok *The Emotions in Early Chinese Philosophy*

Reference: Zong-qi Cai. A Study of Early Chinese Concepts of Qing 情 and a Dialogue with Western Emotion Studies. *Prism*, 17(2) doi: doi:10.1215/25783491-8690428.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: n/a

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: There is discussion on whether or not ghosts and spirits are real. In Sterckx's reading, the Ming gui 明鬼 chapter is not really concerned with ghosts themselves: it is important that people believe in it so that the world is properly governed. If so, then we have a utilitarian usage of this topic, rather than an uninterested debate on the existence of ghosts. Thus, the expression "those who uphold that there are no ghosts 執無鬼者" may be a rhetorical device. The audience of this chapter is not really those people, but rulers or anyone in a position to influence social behavior.

Reference: Roel Sterckx. *mozi 31: explaining ghosts. The Mozi as an Evolving Text*. Brill.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: Since ghosts act on revenge, it is possible to make an argument for the fact that ghosts and non-human entities are assigned what in contemporary scholarships are called emotional states. The text does not elaborated on the emotional life of these entities; it is presented as a fact that ghosts can be happy or not, and act accordingly.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Assuming that the ghosts indicate a form of afterlife. The text does not discuss their origins; perhaps it was discussed in two units of the section on ghosts, Ming gui 明鬼, which did not survive.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: This is not limited to adherents, in fact; the author(s) of the text most likely hoped that what they promoted and believed in would become the standard practice, so our understanding is necessarily partial. Only one of the three chapters debating funeral (節葬) survives. In here, the same principle that guides the logic of this text applies: as long as funeral practices benefit everyone in the society, they can be elaborate. Because this has not been historically true, funerals ought to be moderate.

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Notes: 故古聖王制為葬埋之法，曰：『棺三寸，足以朽體；衣衾三領，足以覆惡。以及其葬也，下毋及泉，上毋通臭，壟若參耕之畝，則止矣。死則既以葬矣，生者必無久哭，而疾而從事，人為其所能，以交相利也。』此聖王之法也。」 "Therefore the ancient sage-kings authorized the code of laws

regarding the burial of the dead thus: The coffin shall be three inches thick, sufficient to hold the body. As to shrouds there shall be three pieces adequate to cover the corpse. It shall not be buried so deep as to reach water and neither so shallow as to allow the odour to ascend. Three feet in size shall be big enough for the mound. There shall be no extended mourning after burial, but speedy return to work and pursuit in what one can do to procure mutual benefit. Such are the laws of the sage-kings." (Legge's translation). ___ Another passage describes how rulers are buried: " There are the outer and the inner coffins, and then the three layers of hide and embroidered covers. When the stones and jade are all collected, there are yet to be completed the spears, swords, dings, pots and ice receptacles, and ten thousand of decorated reins and yokes, and the carriages, horses, and the chorus girls. 必大棺中棺，革闌三操，璧玉即具，戈劍鼎鼓壺盥，文繡素練，大鞅萬領，輿馬女樂皆具，曰必捶塗差通，壟雖凡山陵。" (Legge's translation)

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: The section "節葬 Frugality of burials" actually explicitly advocates against burial goods, considered an unnecessary expense.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Piotr GIBAS. Mozi and the Ghosts: The Concept of ming 明 in Mozi's 'Ming gui' 明鬼..

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The Figure of Shangdi 上帝 (often "Supreme Deity" or "Highest Deity" in English) is referred to, together with ghosts and spirits, as entity to which one ought to sacrifice, or as entity that can reward or punish depending on individuals' behavior. Heaven 天 is another central entity that represents a central authority to which everybody is equally subject. It is difficult to give a comprehensive reading of both these entities, because of the diverse nature of this text. Like with many other ancient texts, it is most likely the result of different hands. See Sterckx 2013 on how this affects e.g. the notion of ghosts and a spiritual world in the Mozi.

Reference: Sarah Allan. ON THE IDENTITY OF SHANG DI 上帝 AND THE ORIGIN OF THE CONCEPT OF A CELESTIAL MANDATE (TIAN MING 天命).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: in the sense that is attributed mental states associated with humans, such as has having desires or being angry

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: it is in fact called "Heaven" 天, as in an entity that resides above the human realm (in fact called "all under Heaven" 天下).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
 - Notes: But in some passages, such as in "法儀 - On the necessity of standards" Heaven is said to have blessed and established as a consequence the ancient emperors.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - No
 - Notes: It depends on the definition of "unquestionably." Heaven for example metes punishments too. In many instances Heaven is said to believe in righteousness, but does this make Heaven itself righteous? One also ought to consider that in many sections, the author(s) make claims with the aim in mind of promoting forms of behavior or socio-political forms of government, which are the real issue of the argument.

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Heaven is all inclusive and impartial, 天之行廣而無私; it has desires, and wants to benefit people who are virtuous.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

Notes: it is actually unclear. The text Mozi, like many others at the time, define the world known to them as "all-under-Heaven," but the boundaries of what is "all-under-Heaven" are never specified.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: 曰無所避逃之。夫天不可為林谷幽門無人，明必見之。"Really there is nowhere to flee. For, Heaven clearly discerns it even if it be in the woods, valleys, or solitary caves where there is no man." (Legge's translation, from 天志上).

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: 曰無所避逃之。夫天不可為林谷幽門無人，明必見之。"Really there is nowhere to flee. For, Heaven clearly discerns it even if it be in the woods, valleys, or solitary caves where there is no man." (Legge's translation, from 天志上).

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: It seems to only act on the past or current state of affairs.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: A section of the 尚賢 middle chapter narrates the stories of ancient kings who succeeded each other, presented as paragons of morality. Heaven

rewarded them because they care for their people, and made them the "Son of Heaven" 天子, (是故天鬼賞之，立為天子) the title used to refer to the person in charge of the political and religious affairs in the known world. By contrast, those who were not caring of their peoples and disrespected their duties, were punished by Heaven (是故天鬼罰之，使身死而為刑戮).

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: see answer to the question before this one.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Unless one considers the thought of being watched as indirect causal efficacy. E.g., Mozi says, almost in an utilitarian fashion, that if people believe spirits reward the worthies, they will behave and the world will be in order. "偕若信鬼神之能賞賢而罰暴也，則夫天下豈亂哉！" 墨子, 明鬼下

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: for example, Heaven blesses (福) rulers (in 法儀)

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: For example, it sends calamities (禍) when rulers are immoral (in 法儀).

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: worshipping spirits (神) and ancestors is not only allowed but in fact encouraged (in form of "serving" 事, or "offering sacrifice" 祀); failing the worshipping of Heaven and spirits leads to disasters, as it happened to the mythical emperor Zhou 紂 (described in chapter 天志)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: n/a

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: There are no explicit references; but it seems implied the Heaven can at any point provide or withdraw his support.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: In the section against offensive warfare (非攻), a story is narrated in which spirits communicate in a dream. But otherwise, there are not explicit references, nor is the topic theorized.

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– I don't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not explicitly states that spirits are human. However, there are references to the fact that the behavior of the living offends the former kings 先王 (as in 非攻下). Given that the text wants people to believe in ghosts and spirits, an argument can be made that the former kings were akin to spirits.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: No definitions of "spirit" 神 or "ghost" 鬼 are given. The text simply assumes that believing in their existence is important, and lists why this would be so. Thus, it is difficult to make a distinction between non-human and human supernatural entities (see answer to previous question).

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

Notes: The text does not specify.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: the text does not specify

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: the text does not specify. I would say yes, since spirits reward or punish according to individuals' behavior

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: the text does not specify. I would say yes, since spirits reward or punish according to individuals' behavior

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: To my understanding, they do not possess knowledge of the future

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: For examples, along with Heaven, ghosts rewarded the ancient sage kings (天鬼賞之), for their moral behavior and love of the people. (in 尚賢中)

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: Conversely to the example above, Heaven and ghosts punished (天鬼罰之) those ancient kings who did not care for their people, and acted abhorrently (in 尚賢中)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: See example of Du Bo 杜伯 in the chapter on spirits, 明鬼.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: in one occasion only, in third section of the chapter against aggressive warfare (非攻), it is narrated that spirits explained Wu in a dream how to overthrow the current, immoral ruler.

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: n/a

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the belief that they exist and mete punishment if a person does not respect an oath or acts immorally should prompt individuals to behave correctly.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– I don't know

Notes: The chapter "Heaven's intentions 天志" mentions food and wine to be sacrificed to the spirits. It is unclear if this is a ritual gesture or if it upholds the idea that supernatural beings possess hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: n/a

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: There are references to groupings such as "the three spirits" 三神; or "Heaven and the ghosts" 天鬼; but I would not argue that these form a pantheon promoted by this text, because we are not here in the presence of a group of goddesses and gods that pertain to a specific religion. The "three spirits" are mentioned only once, thus arguments that they form pantheon would be speculative.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Notes: Lord Mu of Qin 鄭穆公 is said to have seen a spirit with the body of a bird, 鳥身.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: n/a

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Those listed above can be both mysterious and paranormal, depending by the definitions used for these two terms.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: This is concluded on the basis of references to the fact that ghosts can reward or punish the living. This presupposes some sort of monitoring; but the text does not elaborate on the subject.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– No

Notes: Animal sacrifice is mentioned only once with a neutral connotation. In the second section of chapter 尚同, it is said that in ancient times there was a moment when the sage-kings did not dare to use emaciated sacrificial animals. This implies that the practice was at one point in vigor. The same emerges in a passage from "Impartial love" 兼愛, in a speech delivered by Tang 湯 and a drought in Lu's 履 time. In "against offensive warfare" 非攻, animal sacrificed is depicted as negative and/or bearing negative consequences. __ In the third section of the chapter "Impartial Love" 兼愛 (in the same passage cited in previous answer) the text quotes "Oath of Tang" 《湯說》, in which there is a reference to sacrificing the first-born male animal to Heaven to avoid its punishment.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: n/a

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: Those who harm others will be punished by heaven 惡人賊人者，天必禍之; it is further said that the those who kill innocent people, will obtain ill-fortune from it, 殺不辜者，得不祥焉 (in the 法儀 chapter).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– No

Notes: They are not described as actively avoiding risks, nor as in helping the living in doing so.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: n/a

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: For example, the Supreme god and spirits punish humanity when the world is in disorder, 上帝鬼神降之罪厲之禍罰而棄之 (In 節葬下).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

Notes: Meaning "not always." Sometimes it is simply "the spirits" 神 or the "ghosts" 鬼

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: For example, the text says that Heaven punished the kings for not caring for their people. In general, there is a set of behavioral rules that will lead to award (e.g., being moral, acting properly) or punishment (e.g., neglecting one's duties).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: social norms, such as adherence to rituals.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: For examples, along with Heaven, ghosts rewarded the ancient sage kings (天鬼賞之), for their moral behavior and love of the people. (in 尚賢中)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– No

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

Notes: For example, one of the narratives in the "Ming gui 明鬼" tells that Lord Mu of Qin (about 640 B.C.) once saw a spirit, half human half bird. The spirit rewarded him with a long life because of Mu's virtue.

↳ Highly emphasized?
– No

↳ Consists of good luck?
– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: n/a

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the text promotes norms applicable to everyone (caring for each other impartially, being moderate in funerals, behaving morally) that should become conventional. Thus, there is a tension between current rules and values that the author(s) would set as standards.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

Notes: Heaven and spirits reward those who act according to the norms promoted by this text, but I do not think this links the norms to these entities.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

Notes: one may consider generosity present as part of the concept of impartial love 兼愛

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: present as part of the concept of impartial love 兼愛

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: Diligence and self-disciplines may be considered part of the logic of impartial love 兼愛, according to which individuals should prefer what is better for oneself and others to what is just better for oneself.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope
– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

Notes: Although once it is mentioned that particular cleanliness was required during a sacrifice, in the first unit of the chapter "Heaven's intentions." 天志

↳ Other important virtues
– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: see human sacrifice section above

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Details are unclear.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: According to a mention in Han Feizi, individuals identified themselves as followers of Modi's teachings ("墨之所至，墨翟也" Hanfeizi 卷19), thus there was a sense of intellectual, but not religious, identity. ___ The traditionally assigned author of this text, Modi 墨翟, is said to have lived in the state of Lu, one of the states founded during the Zhou dynasty. At any rate, the text is composed by and large by individuals operating during the Warring States era (453-221 BCE), a period of political disunion among the states previously loyal to the Zhou royal family.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: overtime, the formation of empires and the workings of imperial libraries

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The history of the text is rather unknown. There is no record of intentional destruction.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: But almost certainly restricted to women because of the society of which it was part.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: One of the often-discussed theories of the text is that it the Mozi does not condemn war altogether; it condemns aggressive, unprovoked attacks or wars. Logically, if every state embraced this

position, fighting would cease. The text distinguishes three kinds of wars: offensive (攻), which is equal to stealing others' properties and is always wrong; defensive, which is necessary; and punitive (彼非所謂攻, 謂誅也), which is also sometimes necessary. There are three chapters dedicated to the topic, titled "Against offensive [warfare]" .

Reference: Geoffrey Peter Crookes. *Mozi on Warfare: A Critical Analysis of Mohist Military Thought*. PhD Dissertation, University of Calgary (Canada).

Reference: Chris Fraser. *The Mozi and Just War Theory in Pre-Han Thought*.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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